

Possible explanation of the role of the PD ligaments Importance to the growth. Novel suggested mechanism of jaws growth. Supplemental paper

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Abstract

The mechanical properties of the periodontal ligaments are highly difficult to measure and at the same time extremely to be characterized. The effect of the teeth on the growth of the jaws had been investigated by the early researchers. We think that the PD ligament component in the alveolar process is an analogue to the epiphyseal plate. In this paper we had presented a model to highlight the importance of the PD ligaments on the mechanical response of the jaws.

Keywords

Bone stiffness, PD ligaments, Numerical Simulation, Jaws growth, jaws weakening

Introduction

In the previous paper we had made a very important question. A question that had been emerged was

(WHAT IF THE PERIODONTAL HAD DELAYED OR EVEN ACCELERATED RETURN TO THE INITIAL STATUS AFTER THE LOADING?)

This question will address this issue that might add an additional strain caused by the alveolar process and involve the whole jaw, both alveolar process and the basal bone. Although it is very subtle stain, but its effect on the long term will be enormous.

WE SHOULD REMEMBER ALWAYS THAT THE GROWTH IS HAPPEN DUE TO CONTINUOUS RECIPROCAL CUMULATIVE TINY IN AMOUNT BUT HIGH IN MAGNITUDE, ALL OF THESE IS FOR THE DEFORMATION THAT HAPPEN WITHIN DEFORMABLE SUBDOMAIN OF THE SKELETON.

The molecular biology stands as intermediary actor or executor of the predefined genetic plan. As the load occur on the jaws, the teeth will act as response modifier similar to that occur at the epiphyseal growth plate. This is one of conclusive findings from paper of mandibular stiffness and it will be discussed in this supplemental paper.

Teeth are of paramount importance to the growth. (1) The most effect of the teeth presence on the growth is coming from the presence of the PD component, rather that the presence of the teeth and their role in transfer of the load. (2) We here present the strain criteria to evaluate the most deformable component in the whole domain.

The PD ligaments had very complex mechanical response. It had very complex vesico-elastoplastic response. **Invalid source specified.**

Figure 1 (a) Illustration of the linear elastic behavior with full energy recovery, (b) Non-linear viscoelastic behavior (rate dependent: $\dot{\epsilon}$), and (c) viscoplastic behavior.

We think that the load of the jaw could be associated with delayed return due to presence of the teeth. This had not been demonstrated in our current linear model, but it is highly suggested and it is highly accepted concept that could provide an explain for the continuous mandibular advancement with aging. (3) The next model will represent the expansion of the periodontal ligament which is equivalent to the delay in the return after deloading from loaded bone.

In all of the current models we are speaking about passive stiffness

Figure 2 this is the most deformable region of the jaws

In order to demonstrate our proposed theory about jaws growth it is better to introduce a simple more straightforward model to make the analysis and make the results more comprehensible. We had chosen the model we had introduce in our paper about mandibular stiffness to be the current model (4). We think that the deformation in the jaws is not uniform across all the region. The alveolar process, when it invests the teeth with their PD ligament, will behave mechanically different from the base of the jaws. When loaded jaws is deformed, due to function namely mastication or more generalized external force as that occur in case of orthodontic force applied to align the teeth, their viscous part of the response will exert an additional deformation on the whole jaw. The question will arise : **what will happen if the jaw exposed to a deformational force that is resisted by the PD ligaments?** (5) This mismatching in the response, whether the PD ligament have to be expanded or compressed, should be addressed.

Figure 3 This is the idea behind the concept of reciprocating in mandibular exposure to daily activities. In the transition between loading and deloading the will be delay in the return in the upper region of the jaw leading to reciprocal elongation of the lower region

Methods

The model in the paper of effect of the PD on the resorption possible after edentulism. (4) The simulation was linear and we had not tried a plastic deformation as in our paper about the growth associated with the epiphyseal plate

Results and discussions

The simplest way to represent the delay in the return is make an expansion in the PD ligaments. More detailed scrutinization of this model and the assumption behind could change the whole scenario.

Volume: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 4 Outer surface strain in the expanded periodontal ligament model

Figure 5 Better view of the surface strain of the expansion model

Figure 6 Cross section strain in the case of periodontal expansion

The delay in loading of the periodontal ligament will yield the next results. Although this is highly theoretical assumption but it should be held in mind and represented.

Slice: Stored energy density (J/m³)

Figure 7 Cross section of the strain energy density associated with the expansion of the PD ligaments

Figure 8 Outer surface of the strain energy density of the expansion model

Figure 9 The cross section of the strain in the case of shrunken PD ligaments

Volume: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 10 The strain in case of shrunken PD ligaments

Figure 11 Better view of the surface volumetric strain of the shrinkage model

Slice: Stored energy density (J/m³)

Figure 12 Cross section of the strain energy density of the PD ligaments shrinkage

Figure 13 Outer surface of the strain energy density of the shrinkage model

Increase in the displacement, or in another term reduction in the stiffness, is enhanced by the teeth presence. While in the case of implant presence, the stiffness will be enhanced. This will change all the architecture of the jaws bone extending to the base of skull. The strained PD ligament will have great effect on the jaws.

We think that the growth of the jaws is immense at the alveolar process then followed by the basal part

The basal bone is forced to change with delay in the response of the PD ligaments changes

Conclusions

We had proposed an effect of the PD ligaments upon the alveolar process that is followed by changes in the whole jaws. Mechanical characterization of the alveolar process should be investigated as this region will remain having continuous effect on the bones.

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